

success story

Pilot 2: Sustainable Agriculture National scale

Assessing the suitability of land for sustainable agriculture through the lens of Artificial Intelligence

Understanding the suitability of agricultural land for applying specific management practices is of great importance for sustainable and resilient agriculture against climate change. In particular, crop rotation and diversification are by now well established sustainable practices, in line with the Common Agricultural Policy. At the same time, the European agricultural landscape is deeply heterogeneous, with differences in climate, soil, and land use inducing variations in how agricultural systems respond to farmer actions. This reality is now recognized and reflected on high-stakes policy making. In an effort to ensure a sustainable future, the latest iteration of the Common Agricultural Policy (2023-2027) explicitly provides greater flexibility for adapting its measures to local conditions. Clearly, when it comes to choosing management practices, there is no one-size-fits-all approach.

Our Pilot 2 partners at the National Observatory of Athens have now developed an AI solution for assessing the suitability of a piece of land for applying sustainable management practices. Taking into account the particular characteristics of each land unit (e.g. climate and historical land use) and providing the agricultural practice to be tested (crop rotation or diversification), a specialized AI pipeline estimates the impact that the practice will have on green metrics. In that way, the impact of a practice can be assessed in advance, enabling the local adaptation of policy measures, and supercharging the efficiency of sustainable agriculture. The corresponding publication titled “Towards assessing agricultural land suitability with causal machine learning” was accepted for publication at the Earthvision workshop of the 2022 IEEE/CVF Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), the most impactful AI conference of the world. Earthvision is a targeted workshop for the AI4EO community. It is organized for the 3rd consecutive year, frequently featuring prominent researchers and institutions of the field. Accepted Earthvision papers are included in the CVPR 2022 workshop proceedings and published in IEEE Xplore.

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